

Article

Physicochemical Characterisation of Microalgal Biomass: Paving the Way for Industrial Exploitation

César Marina-Montes ^{1,2,*},
Francisco Javier Alarcón ⁴ and Tomás Lafarga ^{1,2}

- ¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Almería, 04120 Almería, Spain
² Desalination and Photosynthesis Functional Unit, CIESOL Solar Energy Research Centre, 04120 Almería, Spain
³ Agroscope, Schwarzenburgstrasse 161, 3003 Bern, Switzerland
⁴ Department of Biology and Geology, University of Almería, 04120 Almería, Spain
⁵ School of Agriculture and Food Science, University College Dublin, D04 V1W8 Dublin, Ireland
* Correspondence: cmarinamontes@ual.es

Abstract

Arthrospira platensis and *Chlorella vulgaris* are popular commercialised microalgae due to their benefits and relatively easy large-scale cultivation. However, recent advances in biotechnology have revealed a new range of promising strains with industrial potential but limited current markets. To bridge the gap in the existing literature, this study provides a comprehensive and simultaneous biochemical characterisation within a unified analytical framework of six additional strains: *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Tetraselmis chunii*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, *Tisochrysis lutea*, and *Skeletonema costatum*. The analyses included macromolecular composition, amino acid and fatty acid profiles, and volatile organic compound composition. Key results identified *P. tricornutum* and *T. chunii* as high-quality protein alternatives, reaching protein concentrations of 31% and 41% (dw), respectively, with essential amino acid profiles (arginine and tryptophan) that match commercial standards. Additionally, specific carbohydrate and lipid strengths were identified: *P. tricornutum* showed a high carbohydrate content (37%), while *N. oceanica* exhibited elevated levels of palmitic, palmitoleic, eicosapentaenoic, and arachidonic acids, marking them as versatile candidates for nutritional applications. Finally, volatile organic compound analyses revealed distinct aroma profiles, highlighting the potential of less-exploited microalgal strains for the food and feed sectors.

Keywords: analysis; renewable resources; protein; lipids; food ingredients

Academic Editor: Jiangyu Zhu
and Minato Wakisaka

Received: 18 January 2026
Revised: 16 February 2026
Accepted: 24 February 2026
Published: 26 February 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors.
Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland.
This article is an open access article
distributed under the terms and
conditions of the [Creative Commons
Attribution \(CC BY\) license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

1. Introduction

Thousands of microalgal strains are preserved in culture collections worldwide, yet only a few have been extensively studied. Even fewer are being produced on a commercial scale, primarily for food applications. These include *Arthrospira platensis* (*AP*; commercially known as *Spirulina*) and *Chlorella vulgaris* (*CV*), both of which are mainly marketed as human food [1–3]. Commercial examples of products containing *AP* and *CV* include *Spirulina* BLU water (FUL Foods, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) and Bio. Algen cracker (FELIX Austria GmbH, Mattersburg, Austria). Other examples are *Dunaliella salina*, a source of β -carotene, and *Haematococcus pluvialis*, which produces and accumulates astaxanthin—both widely used as ingredients in food supplements and functional foods [4,5]. Commercial products include Natural Source Oceanic Beta Carotene capsules (Solgar, Leonia, NJ, USA)

and Astaxanthin capsules (BioProphyl, Nitz, Germany). Today, most of the microalgal biomass is produced using open systems, which are cheaper to build and operate. In general, being open to the environment, these reactors support the production of only extremophile or fast-growing strains [6]. For example, AP is produced in alkaline media (pH 9.5–11.0) [7] and *D. salina* can grow well in media with a conductivity higher than $150 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ [8], limiting the growth of unwanted microorganisms. *H. pluvialis* is an exception. It is not an extremophile, but its capacity to produce and accumulate astaxanthin renders its production using controlled closed photobioreactors operated using artificial illumination economically viable [9]. Indeed, one of the main producers of *H. pluvialis* in Europe (Algalif, Reykjanesbær, Iceland) produces biomass in optimised controlled environments using renewable geothermal energy.

Recent advances in biomass production, including the optimisation of tubular photobioreactors, production indoors using artificial illumination or heterotrophic production using conventional fermenters, open novel opportunities to produce strains that are currently being understudied. These include *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (PT) and *Tisochrysis lutea* (TL). Both strains are produced using tubular photobioreactors [10], but their market is still limited. The former is known to produce and store valuable products such as fucoxanthin or eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) [11], while the latter has been suggested as a potential source of fucoxanthin and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) [12]. However, in-depth characterisations of the composition of these strains have yet to be conducted. The same potential for industrial expansion applies to other emerging strains, such as *Skeletonema costatum* (SC), *Nannochloropsis oceanica* (NO), and *Scenedesmus almeriensis* (SA). While these are currently limited to niche markets like aquafeed, they show significant promise for broader applications. A key example of this transition is *Tetraselmis chunii* (TC), which was authorised in the European Union (EU) as a novel food in 2014 and as a food supplement in 2017, paving the way for its inclusion in the human diet.

Microalgae can be used in the food and feed industries as a source of proteins rich in essential amino acids [13], polyunsaturated fatty acids including EPA and DHA [14], bioactive pigments such as chlorophylls, phycobiliproteins, and carotenoids [15], and other valuable biomolecules including volatile organic compounds (VOCs) [16]. This study bridges a critical knowledge gap by performing a comprehensive biochemical profile of six promising, yet under-exploited, microalgae with significant potential for large-scale production. By comparing these against industrial strains (AC and CV) through a detailed analysis of nutritional and volatile organic compositions, the research identifies key functional attributes that will drive their future industrial adoption.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Microalgae Used

For a complete biochemical characterisation, the following eight microalgal strains were produced at CIESOL (Solar Energy Research Centre) microalgae demonstration plant, University of Almería (Spain): PT, TC, CV; NO, SA, TL, AP, and SC. The biomass production was carried out using 3.1 m^3 tubular photobioreactors located inside a greenhouse ($36^\circ 50' 03.3'' \text{ N } 2^\circ 24' 09.8'' \text{ W}$). Three identical photobioreactors were used simultaneously, each photobioreactor being an experimental unit. Each photobioreactor was equipped with a 0.7 m^3 bubble column 2.3 m tall with a diameter of 0.64 m. The bubble columns were continuously aerated with a constant airflow of around $150 \text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The tubing systems was 28 m long with a tube diameter of 9 cm, arranged in seven parallel conduits on each side. The tubes were fabricated from methacrylate and had a total horizontal length of 400 m. The culture medium consisted of $1.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$ (SQM, Santiago, Chile), $0.16 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Yara, Oslo, Norway), $0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ MgSO}_4$ (I.M.S.A, Albacete, Spain),

0.1 g·L⁻¹ CaCl₂ (Tetra, Spring, TX, USA), and 5 mg·L⁻¹ of a commercial mixture of micronutrients (Karentol®, Konegard, Barcelona, Spain) [17]. SA, CV and AP were produced using freshwater while the other strains were produced using seawater collected directly from the Mediterranean Sea. All the chemicals used were agricultural grade (fertilisers). The biomass production was done in batch mode until the stationary phase was reached. The biomass was harvested using a continuous centrifuge (Ortoalresa, Madrid, Spain), washed using tap water, freeze-dried and stored at -20 °C until further use. Figure 1 shows the colour of the eight freeze-dried samples.

Figure 1. Colour of freeze-dried (A) *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, (B) *Tetraselmis chuii*, (C) *Chlorella vulgaris*, (D) *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, (E) *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, (F) *Tisochrysis lutea*, (G) *Arthrospira platensis*, and (H) *Skeletonema costatum*.

2.2. Macromolecular Composition

Crude protein was measured employing the Kjeldahl method [18], using a protein conversion factor of 5.95. Lipid content was determined gravimetrically following the Folch method using chloroform/methanol (2:1 v/v) as solvent [19]. Moisture and ash content were determined following the standard EN 17605:2022 [20]. Carbohydrate content was calculated as the difference between 100% and the sum of proteins, lipids, ash, and moisture.

2.3. Amino Acid Profile

Total amino acid analysis of the microalgal biomasses was performed using a previously described methodology [21]. Briefly, 100 mg of dried biomass was hydrolysed using 6 N HCl at 110 °C for 24 h. The hydrolysate was then filtered using 0.2 µm Captiva nylon syringe filters (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA), dried under a nitrogen stream, and resuspended in 2 mL of ultrapure water obtained from a Milli-Q system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). Then, 20 µL of this mixture was analysed using a HPLC system (Perkin Elmer Series 200; Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA) equipped with a fluorescence detector (Perkin Elmer Altus A-10; Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA). The separation used a linear gradient over 75 min (Phase A: methanol:acetonitrile, 12:1; Phase B: 23 mM NaOAc, pH 5.95) at flow rate 1 mL·min⁻¹. The amino acid quantification was done in duplicate per natural replicate. Methanol was purchased from Honeywell

(Morristown, NJ, USA) and acetonitrile and NaOAc were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).

2.4. Fatty Acid Profile

Fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were prepared for the characterisation of the fatty acid profiles of the different microalgal samples as described in a previous work [22]. Briefly, approximately 1 g of the sample, 100 μL of internal standard (IS) solution (C23:0 methyl ester in heptane (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain), 10 mg/mL), and 10 mL of potassium hydroxide in methanol (2.5%, *w/v*) were saponified (130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 4 min) in a microwave system (MARS 6 Express 40, CEM Corporation, Matthews, NC, USA). Methanol was purchased from Honeywell (Morristown, NJ, USA) and heptane and potassium hydroxide were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). The samples were cooled to room temperature, and 15 mL of an acetyl chloride solution in methanol (5%, *v/v*) (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) was added to each sample to perform their methyl esterification in the microwave system (120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2 min). The samples were cooled to room temperature, followed by the addition of 10 mL pentane and 20 mL of saturated salt solution to allow the separation of the pentane layers containing FAMES for analysis. Pentane was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). FAMES were separated and quantified using gas chromatography with a flame ionisation detector (GC-FID) using a Clarus 580 gas chromatograph and a capillary column CP-Sil 88 (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA; length: 100 m \times 0.25 mm ID, thickness of film: 0.2 μm). The injection volume was 0.5 μL and hydrogen was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.25 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The initial oven temperature was 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which was increased to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (6.2 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and held at this temperature for 3.2 min before ramping to 240 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (6.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and holding this final temperature for 6.5 min. SupelcoTM FAME mix (Sigma Aldrich, Arklow Co., Wicklow, Ireland) was used as the certified material for the identification of fatty acids, and the integration of the peaks was performed using TotalChrom 6.3.2 (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). The final quantification of each fatty acid was performed based on the IS.

2.5. Volatile Organic Compound Profile

The VOC profiles were determined using a 7890 B gas chromatograph coupled to a 5977 A mass spectrometer (GC-MS), both from Agilent (CA, USA), equipped with an HP-FFAP capillary column (50 m \times 200 μm \times 0.33 μm ; Agilent, CA, USA). The column flow was 1.44 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The oven was operated at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 min and heated at a rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and held for 3 min. The transfer line and ion source temperature were set to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the mass spectrometry was operated in full-scan mode in the 40–400 *m/z* range with hydrogen as carrier gas. The gas phase of the samples was extracted following a previous study [23]. The vacuum pump (V-300; Büchi, Flawil, Switzerland) was operated at 5 mbar. VOC desorption into the cooled injection system (CIS) equipped with a Tenax filled liner (both from Gerstel, Sursee, Switzerland) was done by heating the ITEX trap (BGB Analytik, Rheinfelden, Germany) to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a desorption flow of 150 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 4 min. The solvent vent flow for CIS operation was 20 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The CIS temperature programme started at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, was held for 4 min during desorption, and was then increased to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a rate of 12 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. After each sample, the ITEX trap was cleaned at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min under hydrogen flow. VOC identification with the mass spectrometry data was performed based on spectral comparison with the NIST database (Version NIST17, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA). Match factors above 80% were accepted for identification. Experimental retention indices (RIs) were determined by using an alkane mix (Merck, Buchs, Switzerland) and comparing

the experimental RIs to the literature RIs listed in the NIST database as recommended by the Metabolomics Standard Initiative [24].

The detection of volatile sulphur compounds was performed with a 5380 pulsed-flame photometric detector (PFPD; OI Analytical, College Station, TX, USA) operated in sulphur mode at 250 °C. The GC column flow was split at a 2:1 (MS:PFPD) ratio. The PFPD detector is more sensitive to sulphur compounds than mass spectrometry. However, it does not produce spectra, and sulphur compound standards (Merck, Buchs, Switzerland) were measured for compound identification.

2.6. Statistical Analysis

All the samples were chemically analysed in triplicate ($n = 3$). The data were calculated and reported as the mean \pm standard deviation. All statistical analyses were performed using R Studio software (version 2024.09.01.394). Differences in physicochemical attributes between microalgae were studied by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). When significant differences were obtained ($p < 0.05$), strain means were differentiated using a multiple range test (Tukey's HSD post hoc test).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Macromolecular Composition

The macromolecular composition of the eight strains of microalgae studied is shown in Table 1. Overall, proteins were the most abundant macromolecule, followed by carbohydrates, and lipids, which is in line with what is known for most microalgal strains [25]. The only exception was *PT*, whose most abundant macromolecules were carbohydrates. Together with *NO*, *PT* has been suggested a promising source of lipids, including omega-3 oil for use in the food and feed industries [26,27]. ANOVA results showed significant differences in the protein content of the different strains ($p < 0.001$). For instance, *AP* (*Arthrospira platensis*) and *CV* (64.8%) had the highest protein content ($p < 0.001$). This was not unexpected as both strains are mainly produced for human consumption because of their high protein content and concentration of essential amino acids [28]. The protein concentrations of *AP* and *CV* are in line with the data reported in previous studies [25]. The other strains had a lower protein content, ranging from 31.2% (*PT*) to 41.1% (*TC*). Despite having lower protein content than *AP* and *CV*, levels in these microalgae (*PT*, *TC*, *NO*, *SA*, *TL*, and *SC*) are similar to or even higher than that of most common plant-based protein-rich foods according to the data available in the USDA FoodData Central (<https://fdc.nal.usda.gov>). For example, their protein levels are higher than those of lentils (~24%), chickpeas (~21%), almonds (~21%), peanuts (~23%), oats (~13%) or quinoa (~14%). This supports the role of microalgae as a remarkable protein source.

Table 1. Macromolecular composition of the microalgae studied. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD and are expressed on a dry-weight basis.

Macromolecule	PT (g·100 g ⁻¹)	TC (g·100 g ⁻¹)	CV (g·100 g ⁻¹)	NO (g·100 g ⁻¹)	SA (g·100 g ⁻¹)	TL (g·100 g ⁻¹)	AP (g·100 g ⁻¹)	SC (g·100 g ⁻¹)
Proteins	31.25 \pm 1.2 ^d	41.15 \pm 1.63 ^b	64.85 \pm 0.49 ^a	36 \pm 1.13 ^{bcd}	39.85 \pm 1.91 ^{bc}	33.1 \pm 2.69 ^{cd}	65.95 \pm 2.05 ^a	34.7 \pm 2.26 ^{bcd}
Carbohydrates	37.35 \pm 1.34 ^a	23.75 \pm 6.58 ^{bc}	15.3 \pm 2.26 ^{cd}	21.65 \pm 1.34 ^{bcd}	32.9 \pm 2.26 ^{ab}	31.05 \pm 1.91 ^{ab}	10.4 \pm 1.41 ^d	32.95 \pm 3.32 ^{ab}
Lipids	18.8 \pm 0.85 ^{bc}	23.2 \pm 5.52 ^{ab}	13.3 \pm 1.41 ^c	31.65 \pm 0.64 ^a	17.8 \pm 0.71 ^{bc}	23.65 \pm 0.64 ^{ab}	12.9 \pm 2.55 ^c	14.7 \pm 0.57 ^{bc}
Ashes	12.6 \pm 1.7 ^b	11.9 \pm 0.57 ^b	6.55 \pm 0.35 ^c	10.7 \pm 0.85 ^{bc}	9.45 \pm 0.35 ^{bc}	12.2 \pm 1.41 ^b	10.75 \pm 1.91 ^{bc}	17.65 \pm 0.49 ^a

(PT) *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, (TC) *Tetraselmis chuii*, (CV) *Chlorella vulgaris*, (NO) *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, (SA) *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, (TL) *Tisochrysis lutea*, (AP) *Arthrospira platensis*, and (SC) *Skeletonema costatum*. Different superscript letters within the same row indicate statistically significant differences between strains (Tukey's HSD test, $p < 0.05$).

Carbohydrates were the second most abundant macromolecule in most strains ($p < 0.001$). The highest carbohydrate levels were found in *PT*, *SA* and *SC*, all of which had a similar carbohydrate content of approximately 30%. The lowest concentration (~15%) was found in *AP*, *NO*, and *CV* ($p < 0.05$). Microalgae-derived carbohydrates are actively being widely studied as a promising feedstock for producing third-generation biofuels, partially because microalgal carbohydrate metabolism can be modulated to promote their accumulation [29]. Moreover, significant differences were also observed in the lipid content ($p < 0.001$). The strains *NO*, *TL*, and *TC* showed the highest lipid content (~20–30%), whereas the biomass of *CV* and *AP* had a lipid content of 13.3% and 12.9%, respectively. No significant differences were found in the lipid concentrations of *AP*, *CV*, *SC*, *SA*, and *PT*. Microalgal lipids are a hot trend in different markets [30]. They were first identified as a feedstock to produce biodiesel; however, the yield from large-scale production facilities was far from the theoretical values and their production process remains under investigation [31]. Most of the production processes being developed today aim at using microalgal lipids in the food, feed, chemical and pharmaceutical/cosmetical industries [32]. Finally, significant differences were also observed in the ash content of the biomasses ($p < 0.001$), with values ranging from 6.8% (*CV*) to 17.7% (*SC*). The ash content of *SC* was significantly different from that of the other strains. These values were in line with previous work, such as a hierarchical Bayesian analysis of data compiled from the literature estimating the median content of ash in microalgae growing in nutrient-sufficient media as 17.3% [25].

3.2. Amino Acid Composition

Overall, as mentioned above, proteins were the most abundant macromolecules in all of the studied strains. A complete description of the essential and non-essential amino acid content of the studied strains is presented in Table 2. Regarding essential amino acids, arginine and tryptophan predominated, accounting for 14.3–26.8% of the total protein content (7.6–17.3% on a dry-weight basis). *AP* and *CV* contained ~10% arginine and ~6% tryptophan, respectively. These two strains are mainly used as food, especially as protein sources [33,34]. Their arginine and tryptophan levels were the highest ($p < 0.05$); however, no significant differences were found for the comparison of tryptophan levels of *TC* with both *AP* and *CV*. *CV* also presented a high isoleucine content (6.68%). This amino acid, with values ranging from 2.48% (*TL*) to 4.92% (*AP*), was the third most abundant in all strains except *PT* and *TC*, in which valine ranked third. The content of the remaining essential amino acids ranged from 0.65% lysine (*SA*) to 3.42% leucine (*AP*). Essential amino acids are crucial for survival because the human body cannot synthesise them; hence, they must be obtained through the diet. They serve as building blocks of proteins and play key roles in numerous physiological processes. Given that essential amino acids are mainly present in animal proteins, microalgae rich in essential amino acids are being commercialised as protein supplements for vegan consumers. Microalgae have also been previously used as a source of essential amino acids in wheat-based products, with small proportions of microalgae (1–4%) supplying a higher content of essential amino acids [13].

Among the non-essential amino acids, aspartic and glutamic acids were the most abundant in the microalgal strains, accounting for 18–23% of the total protein content (6–15% on a dry-weight basis). The biomass of *AP* and *CV* had the highest content of these amino acids, mainly because of their higher protein content. The biomass of *AP* contained 5.09% aspartic acid and 9.98% glutamic acid (21.7% of the total protein content), while *CV* had 4.24% and 8.13% (12.4% of the total protein content), respectively. A similar study reported a comparable content of these amino acids in *AP* and *CV*, at 24.5% and 18.8% of the total protein content, respectively [35]. The content of all non-essential amino acids in

AP, with the exceptions of glycine (which showed no significant differences compared to CV, PT, and TL) and alanine (no significant differences compared to CV), were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from those of other strains. Alanine was the third most abundant non-essential amino acid in all strains, except for NO and SC, where tyrosine and serine were more abundant.

Table 2. Amino acid profiles of the studied microalgae. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD and are expressed on a dry-weight basis.

Amino Acid	PT (g·100 g ⁻¹)	TC (g·100 g ⁻¹)	CV (g·100 g ⁻¹)	NO (g·100 g ⁻¹)	SA (g·100 g ⁻¹)	TL (g·100 g ⁻¹)	AP (g·100 g ⁻¹)	SC (g·100 g ⁻¹)	
Non-essential	Aspartic acid (D)	4.18 \pm 0.17 ^b	3.63 \pm 0.13 ^{bc}	4.24 \pm 0.15 ^b	2.79 \pm 0.08 ^{de}	2.53 \pm 0.14 ^e	3.7 \pm 0.2 ^{bc}	5.09 \pm 0.31 ^a	3.36 \pm 0.2 ^{cd}
	Glutamic acid (E)	7.41 \pm 0.31 ^{bc}	6.15 \pm 0.22 ^{cd}	8.13 \pm 0.28 ^b	7.32 \pm 0.21 ^{bc}	4.03 \pm 0.22 ^e	5.28 \pm 0.29 ^{de}	9.98 \pm 0.61 ^a	6.37 \pm 0.39 ^{cd}
	Serine (S)	2.49 \pm 0.1 ^{bc}	2.32 \pm 0.08 ^{bc}	2.32 \pm 0.08 ^{bc}	2.78 \pm 0.08 ^b	1.84 \pm 0.1 ^d	2.27 \pm 0.12 ^{cd}	3.32 \pm 0.2 ^a	2.38 \pm 0.14 ^{bc}
	Glycine (G)	2.23 \pm 0.09 ^{bcd}	1.75 \pm 0.06 ^e	2.54 \pm 0.09 ^b	3.03 \pm 0.09 ^a	1.03 \pm 0.06 ^f	2.01 \pm 0.11 ^{cde}	2.35 \pm 0.14 ^{bc}	1.89 \pm 0.12 ^{de}
	Alanine (A)	3.26 \pm 0.13 ^{bc}	2.97 \pm 0.11 ^{cd}	3.55 \pm 0.12 ^{ab}	3.28 \pm 0.09 ^{bc}	2.02 \pm 0.11 ^e	2.49 \pm 0.14 ^{de}	3.99 \pm 0.24 ^a	2.12 \pm 0.13 ^e
	Tyrosine (Y)	2.52 \pm 0.1 ^{bc}	2.08 \pm 0.08 ^{cd}	2.47 \pm 0.09 ^{bc}	2.67 \pm 0.08 ^b	1.58 \pm 0.09 ^e	1.89 \pm 0.1 ^{de}	3.55 \pm 0.22 ^a	1.84 \pm 0.11 ^{de}
	Proline (P)	2.41 \pm 0.03 ^b	2.18 \pm 0.08 ^c	1.93 \pm 0.06 ^d	3.46 \pm 0.07 ^a	1.02 \pm 0.02 ^g	1.57 \pm 0.03 ^e	1.7 \pm 0.02 ^e	1.37 \pm 0.04 ^f
	Arginine (R)	6.97 \pm 0.29 ^b	4.4 \pm 0.16 ^d	10.57 \pm 0.36 ^a	4.76 \pm 0.14 ^{cd}	4.57 \pm 0.25 ^{cd}	4.74 \pm 0.26 ^{cd}	11.03 \pm 0.67 ^a	5.8 \pm 0.35 ^{bc}
	Histidine (H)	1.36 \pm 0.06 ^b	1.26 \pm 0.05 ^{bc}	1.63 \pm 0.06 ^a	1.49 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}	0.82 \pm 0.04 ^d	1.03 \pm 0.06 ^{cd}	1.41 \pm 0.09 ^{ab}	1.4 \pm 0.08 ^{ab}
	Threonine (T)	2.25 \pm 0.09 ^b	1.88 \pm 0.07 ^{bcd}	2.08 \pm 0.07 ^{bc}	2.65 \pm 0.08 ^a	1.39 \pm 0.08 ^e	1.75 \pm 0.09 ^{cde}	2.77 \pm 0.17 ^a	1.63 \pm 0.1 ^{de}
Essential	Valine (V)	3.13 \pm 0.04 ^{bc}	3.12 \pm 0.11 ^c	3.39 \pm 0.1 ^b	3.4 \pm 0.07 ^b	1.92 \pm 0.04 ^e	2.36 \pm 0.05 ^d	3.78 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.99 \pm 0.06 ^e
	Methionine (M)	1.79 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.83 \pm 0.06 ^b	1.63 \pm 0.05 ^c	2.08 \pm 0.04 ^a	0.99 \pm 0.02 ^e	1.55 \pm 0.03 ^{cd}	2.17 \pm 0.03 ^a	1.4 \pm 0.04 ^d
	Tryptophan (W)	5.89 \pm 0.08 ^b	6.1 \pm 0.21 ^{ab}	6.57 \pm 0.19 ^a	2.86 \pm 0.06 ^e	4.3 \pm 0.09 ^d	5.21 \pm 0.11 ^c	6.27 \pm 0.09 ^{ab}	3.8 \pm 0.11 ^d
	Phenylalanine (F)	2.64 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}	1.88 \pm 0.06 ^d	2.43 \pm 0.07 ^c	2.82 \pm 0.06 ^a	1.46 \pm 0.03 ^e	1.87 \pm 0.04 ^d	2.58 \pm 0.04 ^{bc}	1.89 \pm 0.05 ^d
	Isoleucine (I)	2.54 \pm 0.04 ^d	2.48 \pm 0.09 ^d	6.68 \pm 0.19 ^a	4.02 \pm 0.08 ^c	3.83 \pm 0.08 ^c	2.47 \pm 0.05 ^d	4.92 \pm 0.07 ^b	2.57 \pm 0.07 ^d
	Leucine (L)	1.75 \pm 0.03 ^d	1.71 \pm 0.06 ^d	2.02 \pm 0.06 ^c	2.78 \pm 0.06 ^b	1.19 \pm 0.03 ^e	1.72 \pm 0.04 ^d	3.42 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.77 \pm 0.05 ^d
	Lysine (K)	1.06 \pm 0.02 ^d	1.21 \pm 0.04 ^c	1.7 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.33 \pm 0.03 ^b	0.66 \pm 0.01 ^f	0.85 \pm 0.02 ^e	1.1 \pm 0.02 ^d	0.65 \pm 0.02 ^f
	TOTAL	53.85 \pm 1.04	46.97 \pm 0.25	63.89 \pm 0.53	53.30 \pm 0.41	35.12 \pm 0.75	42.76 \pm 0.99	69.43 \pm 2.28	42.26 \pm 1.19

(PT) *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, (TC) *Tetraselmis chuii*, (CV) *Chlorella vulgaris*, (NO) *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, (SA) *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, (TL) *Tisochrysis lutea*, (AP) *Arthrospira platensis*, and (SC) *Skeletonema costatum*. Different superscript letters within the same row indicate statistically significant differences between strains (Tukey’s HSD test, $p < 0.05$).

3.3. Fatty Acid Composition

In this study, 12 major fatty acids (>0.5% of the total composition in any strain on a dry-weight basis) and 26 minor fatty acids (<0.5%) were identified. The results of the fatty acid determination are provided in Table 3. Overall, among the major fatty acids, myristic acid (C14:0), palmitic acid (C16:0), palmitoleic acid (C16:1n7c), linoleic acid (C18:2n6t), α -linolenic acid (C18:3n3c), and eicosapentaenoic acid (C20:5n3c) were present at concentrations exceeding 1% in at least one strain. Meanwhile, oleic acid (C18:1n9c), vaccenic acid (C18:1n7c), linoleic acid (C18:2n6c), γ -linolenic acid (C18:3n6c), arachidonic acid (C20:4n6c), and docosahexaenoic acid (C22:6n3c) were detected at concentrations between 0.5 and 1.0% in at least one strain. Several minor fatty acids, such as caproic acid (C6:0), stearic acid (C18:0), lauric acid (C12:0), and lignoceric acid (C24:0), were detected, each contributing to less than 0.5% of the total composition on a dry-weight basis. These minor fatty acids were not included in the comparative analysis. Concerning the saturated fatty acids (SFAs), TL exhibited the highest concentration of myristic acid (1094.7 mg·100 g⁻¹), followed by SC (983.4 mg·100 g⁻¹) and NO (902.7 mg·100 g⁻¹). The myristic acid concentration in TL was significantly different ($p < 0.001$) from that of all other strains. Its concentrations in SC and NO were also statistically different ($p < 0.001$). Palmitic acid was the most abundant in NO (3980.7 mg·100 g⁻¹), with significant differences found compared to all the studied strains ($p < 0.001$). The second highest concentration of palmitic acid was found in CV (1926.5 mg·100 g⁻¹). Moreover, significant differences were observed

between the content of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) in the different strains studied ($p < 0.001$). For example, the highest concentration of palmitoleic acid was observed in the biomass of *NO* ($3683.8 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The second highest concentration of palmitoleic acid was found in *PT* ($1295.6 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), followed by *SC* ($927.7 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Oleic acid showed the highest concentration in *CV* ($931.2 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), which was significantly different from the other strains ($p < 0.001$). The second and third strains with the highest content of oleic acid were *PT* ($659.9 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and *NO* ($540.6 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), with significant differences between them ($p < 0.001$). No significant differences were observed in the oleic acid content of *TL* and *SA* ($\sim 500 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). *CV* also had the highest content of vaccenic acid ($828.5 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), with significant differences found compared to the other strains ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Fatty acid composition of the microalgae studied. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations \pm SD and are expressed on a dry-weight basis.

FAME	PT ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	TC ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	CV ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	NO ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	SA ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	TL ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	AP ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	SC ($\text{mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$)
C6:0 Caproic acid ME	nd	nd	0.62 ± 0.88^b	2.83 ± 0.07^a	nd	nd	nd	3.17 ± 0.13^a
C8:0 Caprylic acid ME	nd	nd	nd	39.53 ± 0.15^a	nd	0.3 ± 0.42^b	nd	0.4 ± 0.56^b
C10:0 Capric acid ME	nd	nd	nd	27.58 ± 0.84^a	nd	nd	nd	2.77 ± 0.09^b
C11:0 Undecanoic acid ME	1.51 ± 0.01^d	2.88 ± 0.07^c	nd	nd	nd	12.72 ± 0.15^a	nd	8.34 ± 0.2^b
C12:0 Lauric acid ME	3.48 ± 0.03^{cd}	0.51 ± 0.72^d	4.72 ± 3.08^{cd}	98.92 ± 0.23^a	12.19 ± 3.59^b	8.21 ± 0.09^{bc}	6.23 ± 1^{bcd}	7.11 ± 0.11^{bcd}
C13:0 Tridecanoic acid ME	35.59 ± 0.04^d	29.95 ± 2.19^e	85.61 ± 2.76^a	79.67 ± 0.15^b	69.04 ± 0.18^c	35.52 ± 0.14^d	15.95 ± 0.04^g	22.69 ± 0.34^f
C14:0 Myristic acid ME	437.16 ± 2.08^d	28.59 ± 2.12^e	27.93 ± 0.18^e	902.74 ± 1.08^c	27 ± 0.26^e	1094.76 ± 4.58^a	15.97 ± 0.71^e	983.41 ± 7.29^b
C14:1n5c Myristoleic acid ME	0.71 ± 0.05^c	nd	nd	8.91 ± 2.76^b	nd	25.85 ± 0.08^a	nd	26.15 ± 1.36^a
C15:0 Pentadecanoic acid ME	25.84 ± 0.21^c	4.54 ± 0.87^g	8.52 ± 0.1^f	69.18 ± 0.15^a	11.7 ± 1.21^e	33.75 ± 0.87^b	1.91 ± 0.27^g	16.4 ± 1.34^d
C15:1n5c Pentadecenoic acid ME	0.61 ± 0.01^b	nd	nd	nd	0.47 ± 0.66^b	0.35 ± 0.5^b	nd	2.64 ± 0.97^a
C16:0 Palmitic acid ME	885.76 ± 3.93^d	830.78 ± 65.24^{de}	1926.55 ± 1.36^b	3980.76 ± 1.98^a	1185.38 ± 3.18^c	697.31 ± 4.61^e	1212.21 ± 96.97^c	268.46 ± 0.33^f
C16:1n7c Palmitoleic acid ME	1295.61 ± 5.14^b	0 ± 0^b	57.5 ± 0.1^g	3683.86 ± 2.92^a	104.94 ± 0.14^f	590.4 ± 2.63^d	135.46 ± 10.94^e	927.75 ± 3.98^c
C17:0 Heptadecanoic acid ME	4.03 ± 0.06^d	43.2 ± 3.47^a	13.9 ± 0.05^c	24.47 ± 0.37^b	16.71 ± 0.03^c	2.28 ± 0^d	5.11 ± 2.08^d	6.54 ± 0.2^d
C17:1n7c Heptadecenoic acid ME	nd	nd	nd	nd	6.19 ± 0.53	nd	nd	nd
C18:0 Stearic acid ME	18.31 ± 1.83^d	9.14 ± 1.18^{de}	76.81 ± 0.45^b	96.74 ± 7.12^a	37.51 ± 0.55^c	7 ± 0.03^e	31.21 ± 2.6^c	nd
C18:1n9t Elaidic acid ME	3.22 ± 0.47^b	nd	nd	nd	6.77 ± 1.33^{ab}	7.57 ± 0.55^a	6.08 ± 2.31^{ab}	7.89 ± 0.66^a
C18:1n7t Vaccenic acid ME	nd	nd	1.73 ± 0.37^b	17.23 ± 0.02^a	1.45 ± 0.9^b	nd	nd	nd
C18:1n9c Oleic acid ME	659.91 ± 2.92^b	327.88 ± 21.21^f	931.24 ± 1.05^a	540.65 ± 0.85^c	489.44 ± 0.75^d	503.81 ± 2.58^d	205.24 ± 13.81^g	448.11 ± 3.1^e
C18:1n7c Vaccenic acid ME	64.66 ± 0.24^e	88.47 ± 6.71^d	828.54 ± 2.54^a	100.13 ± 0.09^d	325.66 ± 0.54^b	143.03 ± 5.63^c	64.78 ± 0.98^e	30.12 ± 0.12^f

Table 3. Cont.

FAME	PT (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	TC (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	CV (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	NO (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	SA (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	TL (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	AP (mg·100 g ⁻¹)	SC (mg·100 g ⁻¹)
C18:2n6t Linolelaidic acid ME	0.97 ± 0.02 ^d	1.39 ± 0.34 ^{cd}	2707.55 ± 1.44 ^a	5.8 ± 0.78 ^b	3.4 ± 0.11 ^c	nd	nd	3.08 ± 0.18 ^{cd}
C18:2n6c Linoleic acid ME	394.04 ± 0.71 ^c	172.78 ± 13.73 ^d	11.14 ± 0.06 ^e	405.74 ± 2.71 ^c	697.04 ± 0.13 ^a	496.54 ± 1.66 ^b	377.1 ± 31.55 ^c	161.79 ± 0.99 ^d
C20:0 Arachidic acid ME	6.89 ± 0.29 ^c	0.29 ± 0.4 ^e	11.14 ± 0.06 ^b	13.29 ± 0.21 ^a	4.17 ± 0.03 ^d	3.7 ± 0.01 ^d	3.27 ± 0.64 ^d	nd
C18:3n6c Gamma- linolenic acid ME	11.72 ± 0.92 ^b	63.66 ± 5.13 ^b	9.15 ± 0.09 ^b	61.2 ± 0.04 ^b	40.97 ± 0.15 ^b	65.93 ± 0.46 ^b	567.71 ± 42.77 ^a	12.67 ± 0.17 ^b
C20:1n9c 11-Eicosenoic acid ME	nd	68.64 ± 5.63 ^a	4.37 ± 0.18 ^b	0.42 ± 0.59 ^b	5.28 ± 7.46 ^b	2.79 ± 0.38 ^b	8.26 ± 0.47 ^b	nd
C18:3n3 Alpha- linolenic acid ME	117.3 ± 0.57 ^e	636.06 ± 50.67 ^c	973.85 ± 0.45 ^b	8.53 ± 0.44 ^f	2374.74 ± 1.21 ^a	556.97 ± 2.7 ^d	72.49 ± 4.5 ^{ef}	19.79 ± 1.96 ^f
C21:0 Hemicosanoic acid ME	1.89 ± 0.03 ^b	nd	nd	13.42 ± 0.25 ^a	nd	nd	nd	nd
C20:2n6c 11,14- Eisodienoic acid ME	6.29 ± 1.97 ^b	nd	10.04 ± 1.14 ^a	4.63 ± 0.41 ^b	nd	nd	2.79 ± 1.32 ^b	nd
C22:0 Behenic acid ME	30.88 ± 0.09 ^a	1.17 ± 0.1 ^e	6.91 ± 0.16 ^d	30.03 ± 0.23 ^{ab}	27.78 ± 0.06 ^b	17.56 ± 0.02 ^c	0.88 ± 1.25 ^e	2.61 ± 0.98 ^e
C20:3n6c 8,11,14- Eicosatrienoic acid ME	nd	2.03 ± 1.66 ^b	nd	42.61 ± 0.52 ^a	3.81 ± 0.24 ^b	7.69 ± 4.28 ^b	6.39 ± 0.77 ^b	1.6 ± 2.26 ^b
C22:1n9c Eruic acid ME	3.99 ± 0.33 ^c	nd	7.78 ± 0.79 ^b	2.09 ± 0.02 ^c	nd	16.67 ± 1.33 ^a	nd	8.53 ± 1.03 ^b
C20:3n3c 11,14,17- Eicosatrienoic acid ME	5.34 ± 0.07 ^a	1.39 ± 1.97 ^b	nd	nd	2.15 ± 0.04 ^b	4.08 ± 0.12 ^{ab}	nd	nd
C20:4n6c Arachidonic acid ME	25.99 ± 0.05 ^b	24.92 ± 3.34 ^{bc}	5.12 ± 0.18 ^c	849.48 ± 2.65 ^a	22.55 ± 0.63 ^{bc}	nd	9.75 ± 13.78 ^{bc}	26.62 ± 0.34 ^b
C22:2n6c 13,16- Docosadienoic acid ME	nd	nd	nd	15.63 ± 0.31	nd	nd	nd	nd
C24:0 Lignoceric acid ME	132.34 ± 0.51 ^a	3.2 ± 4.52 ^d	16.37 ± 0.06 ^b	12.95 ± 0.07 ^{bc}	8.39 ± 0.22 ^{cd}	4.22 ± 0.25 ^d	nd	8.17 ± 0.15 ^{cd}
C20:5n3c 5,8,11,14,17- Eisopentaenoic acid ME	1776.94 ± 5.88 ^b	175.02 ± 14.65 ^d	20.79 ± 0.62 ^e	3424.78 ± 27.27 ^a	40.67 ± 2.2 ^e	45.83 ± 0.25 ^e	25.36 ± 1.1 ^e	341.17 ± 1.31 ^c
C24:1n9c Nervonic acid ME	15.66 ± 0.49 ^a	nd	11.64 ± 0.09 ^b	nd	nd	6.97 ± 0.26 ^c	nd	1.73 ± 2.45 ^d
C22:5n3c 7,10,13,16,19 Docosapen- taenoic acid ME	6.46 ± 0.16 ^{bc}	2.55 ± 3.6 ^{bc}	3.36 ± 0.47 ^{bc}	15.89 ± 0.23 ^a	1.65 ± 2.33 ^c	3.66 ± 0.32 ^{bc}	nd	8.27 ± 1.12 ^b
C22:6n3c 4,7,10,13,16,19 Docosahex- aenoic acid ME	53.7 ± 0.01 ^b	7.53 ± 0.35 ^c	nd	9.2 ± 0.6 ^c	nd	810.23 ± 11.46 ^a	6.06 ± 0.68 ^c	37.94 ± 0.14 ^b
TOTAL	6026.81 ± 29.19	2526.57 ± 209.88	7762.87 ± 18.70	14,588.87 ± 56.12	5527.08 ± 28.66	5205.70 ± 46.33	2780.21 ± 230.55	3395.92 ± 33.86

(PT) *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, (TC) *Tetraselmis chuii*, (CV) *Chlorella vulgaris*, (NO) *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, (SA) *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, (TL) *Tisochrysis lutea*, (AP) *Arthrospira platensis*, and (SC) *Skeletonema costatum*. Different superscript letters within the same row indicate statistically significant differences between strains (Tukey's HSD test, $p < 0.05$).

Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) are a type of dietary fat that are considered essential for humans [30]. They are characterised by having two or more carbon–carbon double bonds giving them unique properties. Several PUFAs were identified. Linolelaidic acid is an isomer of linoleic acid and is included in the group of omega-6 fatty acids. The highest concentration of this compound was observed in *CV* ($2707.5 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$; $p < 0.001$). The remaining strains had very low levels of this fatty acid, ranging from 0 to $5.8 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$. For α -linolenic acid, *SA* exhibited the highest concentration ($2374.7 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$; $p < 0.001$). The second, third, and fourth highest concentrations of α -linolenic acid were found in *CV* ($973.8 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), *TC* ($636.0 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), and *TL* ($556.9 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). α -Linolenic acid belongs to the omega-3 family and is a precursor of other essential fatty acids such as eicosapentaenoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid. These two fatty acids also belong to the omega-3 family and are important for their health-promoting properties, including brain development and function. In this study, *NO* showed the highest concentration of eicosapentaenoic ($3424.7 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$; $p < 0.001$), followed by *PT* ($1776.9 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and *SC* ($341.1 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Marine microalgae including *Nannochloropsis* strains are widely investigated as a source of eicosapentaenoic acid [36]. *SA* exhibited the highest concentration of linoleic acid ($697.0 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and *AP* showed the highest γ -linolenic acid concentration ($567.7 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The highest concentration of arachidonic acid was observed in *NO* ($849.48 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$; $p < 0.001$). In the other strains the concentration of arachidonic acid ranged from $0 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (*TL*) to $26.6 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (*SC*). Finally, *TL* exhibited the highest docosahexaenoic acid concentration, with a marked difference compared to the remaining strains ($0\text{--}53.7 \text{ mg}\cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$).

Overall, *NO* showed the highest concentrations of palmitic, palmitoleic, eicosapentaenoic, and arachidonic acids, while *TL* had the highest concentrations of myristic and docosahexaenoic acids. In addition, *CV* was distinguished for its linolelaidic, oleic, and vaccenic acid content, whereas *SA* exhibited the highest α -linolenic and linoleic acid concentrations. *AP* had the highest concentration of γ -linolenic acid. The fatty acid composition of the studied strains, particularly in *NO*, reinforces their potential as a high-value source of PUFAs for nutraceutical applications [37].

3.4. Volatile Organic Compounds

Microalgae are widely recognised for their high nutritional value, offering a rich source of proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids [38]. However, aroma plays a pivotal role in consumer acceptance. Certain molecules impart unpleasant aromas to the dried biomass of algae and microalgae [39]. These include, among others, geosmin (earthy, musty), dimethyl sulphide (fishy, marine), and oxidised lipids (rancid) [40]. As aroma is shaped by a wide array of different VOCs, the analysis of VOCs is essential for both aroma characterisation and the evaluation of nutritional value. Additionally, the VOC profile provides valuable insights into the metabolic processes of microalgae. VOCs in microalgae can arise from several metabolic pathways, predominantly amino acid and fatty acid metabolism, and can serve as biomarkers for growth phase and culture fitness [41].

In this study, a diverse range of VOCs was identified in the different microalgae samples. The wide diversity of VOCs identified establishes a unique ‘sensory fingerprint’ for each strain, making it possible to strategically select microalgae based on the desired aromatic profile of the final food product [42]. These compounds were classified into various substance groups, including alkanes, alkenes, aldehydes, ketones, alcohols, acids, esters, amides, sulphur compounds, and unknown compounds. A comprehensive list of the identified compounds is provided in Table 4 and specific aroma and analysed properties are listed in Supplementary Table S1. The distribution of these substance classes among the microalgae is visualised in Figure 2. Sulphur compounds were examined separately

using a pulsed-flame photometric detector, as their scale was not directly comparable to the mass spectrometry results. Alkanes, alkenes and alkynes are known to have a low aroma impact. Alkanes exhibited a wide distribution ranging from 1 to 48% among the microalgae, with the lowest proportion in SC and the highest in AP. By contrast, alkenes were present at levels below 12%. Aldehydes contributing fresh, green, herbal, spicy and fruity notes [42] were consistently present at levels of <4% across all samples, indicating a limited influence on the overall aroma profile. Ketones, typically associated with sweet, woody, fruity, floral, and herbal notes perceived as pleasant [41], ranged from 1 to 20%, with the highest abundance in TC and the lowest in NO.

Figure 2. Percentual distribution of volatile compounds for the different microalgal strains. Sulphur compounds are displayed separately as they were measured with a pulsed-flame photometric detector, and the scale is not comparable to the mass spectrometric results.

Table 4. Relative abundance of volatile organic compounds (arbitrary area units) of the studied strains. Values represent mean values of three independent determinations \pm S.D.

VOC	Retention Time (min)	PT (AAU·10 ³)	TC (AAU·10 ³)	CV (AAU·10 ³)	NO (AAU·10 ³)	SA (AAU·10 ³)	TL (AAU·10 ³)	AP (AAU·10 ³)	SC (AAU·10 ³)
Aldehydes									
Hexanal	9.699	139.04 \pm 17.19 ^{ef}	319.26 \pm 8.6 ^{cd}	380.67 \pm 18.75 ^c	562.64 \pm 26.72 ^b	85.68 \pm 5.06 ^f	235.67 \pm 22.67 ^{de}	492.35 \pm 52.98 ^b	935.48 \pm 21.03 ^a
Heptanal	11.895	14.79 \pm 2.95 ^c	26 \pm 0.69 ^c	25.26 \pm 0.82 ^c	73.31 \pm 4.28 ^b	14.52 \pm 1.17 ^c	29.36 \pm 1.04 ^c	19.72 \pm 1.49 ^c	951.34 \pm 12.8 ^a
Alkanes									
Decane	7.338	917.24 \pm 188.63 ^b	15.61 \pm 5.21 ^c	nd	2119.2 \pm 30.4 ^a	6.96 \pm 1.2 ^c	49.65 \pm 7.24 ^c	15.99 \pm 1.5 ^c	22.16 \pm 3.74 ^c
Dodecane	11.984	1585.88 \pm 291.89 ^b	203.15 \pm 5.56 ^c	138.82 \pm 12.64 ^c	3106.62 \pm 74.94 ^a	152.47 \pm 3.94 ^c	383.98 \pm 24.91 ^c	164.46 \pm 4.53 ^c	171.86 \pm 3.54 ^c
Pentadecane	16.648	371.81 \pm 89.7 ^{ab}	323.04 \pm 31.99 ^{abc}	235.53 \pm 37.1 ^{bcd}	361.09 \pm 7.06 ^{abc}	249.11 \pm 26.67 ^{bcd}	441.99 \pm 4.85 ^a	219.19 \pm 14.07 ^{cd}	131.44 \pm 8.62 ^d
Tetradecane	15.254	830.38 \pm 56.4 ^b	122.54 \pm 1.08 ^{cd}	119.83 \pm 10.01 ^{cd}	1001.95 \pm 65.87 ^a	124.18 \pm 6.6 ^{cd}	194.58 \pm 7.55 ^c	110.23 \pm 7.41 ^{cd}	63.95 \pm 20.99 ^d
Hexadecane	17.984	117.48 \pm 18.01 ^d	107.72 \pm 11.29 ^d	118.23 \pm 3.24 ^d	503.87 \pm 128.3 ^{bc}	564.68 \pm 22.51 ^b	107.64 \pm 10.62 ^d	4358.89 \pm 225.59 ^a	141.74 \pm 6.36 ^{cd}
Heptadecane	19.175	32.22 \pm 4.31 ^d	36.85 \pm 5.22 ^d	2316.3 \pm 137.74 ^{cd}	4964.27 \pm 149.57 ^{bc}	7809.07 \pm 182.87 ^b	38,817.5 \pm 2652.36 ^a	38,817.5 \pm 2562.4	nd
Alkenes/Alkynes									
1-Pentadecene	17.338	3733.92 \pm 388.54 ^a	320.49 \pm 27.8 ^c	76 \pm 2.44 ^c	3842.36 \pm 43.04 ^a	125.97 \pm 1.94 ^c	1256.08 \pm 54.38 ^b	37.2 \pm 0.27 ^c	299.21 \pm 0.89 ^c
8-Heptadecene	19.485	nd	23.58 \pm 5.78 ^d	347.91 \pm 25.99 ^c	1167.99 \pm 26.08 ^a	691.12 \pm 18.91 ^b	1223.51 \pm 70.8 ^a	32.55 \pm 13.56 ^d	32.5 \pm 13.6
1-Heptadecene	19.784	22.11 \pm 3.98 ^b	2.63 \pm 0.31 ^d	3.34 \pm 0.22 ^d	319.56 \pm 4.43 ^a	nd	10.84 \pm 1.55 ^{cd}	13.69 \pm 1.26 ^{bc}	3.8 \pm 0.07 ^d
1,7-Hexadecadiene	20.386	289.19 \pm 48.7 ^a	nd	nd	48.33 \pm 0.32 ^b	nd	nd	nd	nd
Ketones									
3,5-Octadien-2-one	17.252	983.21 \pm 56.95 ^b	3076.14 \pm 271.32 ^a	173.38 \pm 9.81 ^d	664.21 \pm 9.58 ^{bc}	449.55 \pm 12.63 ^{cd}	892.67 \pm 62.96 ^{bc}	2936.33 \pm 83.76 ^a	2936.3 \pm 83.6
α -Ionone	21.257	3.74 \pm 0.87 ^d	2140.67 \pm 82.57 ^a	494.97 \pm 7.87 ^b	25.02 \pm 0.04 ^d	175.36 \pm 0.9 ^c	2.03 \pm 0.49 ^d	10.18 \pm 4.09 ^d	6.69 \pm 2.27 ^d
3-Buten-2-one, 4-(2,6,6-trimethyl-1-cyclohexen-1-yl)-	22.218	566.56 \pm 23.22 ^d	3106.66 \pm 71.43 ^a	425.91 \pm 3.29 ^{ef}	831.3 \pm 0.02 ^c	351.31 \pm 0.1 ^f	379.06 \pm 19.19 ^f	1129.23 \pm 37.11 ^b	511.29 \pm 2.64 ^{de}
2-Pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-	23.848	19.08 \pm 2.01 ^b	28.23 \pm 1.8 ^b	4.54 \pm 0.31 ^b	18.78 \pm 0.77 ^b	5.42 \pm 0.35 ^b	10.36 \pm 0.08 ^b	1.28 \pm 0.03 ^b	256.99 \pm 25.15 ^a
1H-Pyrrole-2,5-dione, 3-ethyl-4-methyl-	25.473	56.22 \pm 3.56 ^c	116.45 \pm 3.03 ^b	39.83 \pm 1.77 ^c	97.6 \pm 5.76 ^b	10.22 \pm 0.64 ^d	18.28 \pm 1.36 ^d	7.51 \pm 1.86 ^d	324.1 \pm 12.73 ^a
2(4H)-Benzofuranone, 5,6,7,7a-tetrahydro-4,4,7a-trimethyl-, (R)-	26.576	755.34 \pm 25.34 ^b	1205.34 \pm 7.87 ^a	179.08 \pm 11.96 ^f	586.11 \pm 15.64 ^c	133.31 \pm 1.58 ^f	408.45 \pm 14.28 ^{de}	429.47 \pm 34.49 ^d	341.29 \pm 15.5 ^e

Table 4. Cont.

VOC	Retention Time (min)	PT (AAU·10 ³)	TC (AAU·10 ³)	CV (AAU·10 ³)	NO (AAU·10 ³)	SA (AAU·10 ³)	TL (AAU·10 ³)	AP (AAU·10 ³)	SC (AAU·10 ³)
Alcohols									
1-Penten-3-ol	11.347	1309.39 ± 85.96 ^c	2560.1 ± 466.33 ^b	121.67 ± 1.82 ^d	3180.04 ± 143.38 ^b	395.28 ± 9.04 ^d	1629 ± 87.33 ^c	21.9 ± 3.05 ^d	8814.08 ± 246.41 ^a
1-Butanol, 3-methyl-	12.268	130.17 ± 139.98 ^b	225.33 ± 62.41 ^b	259.37 ± 73.62 ^b	nd	108.91 ± 6.57 ^b	145.01 ± 6.78 ^b	74.02 ± 17.63 ^b	1659.88 ± 84.51 ^a
1-Hexen-3-ol	13.029	370.02 ± 12.3 ^b	78.53 ± 9.75 ^{bc}	34.28 ± 7.21 ^c	8.17 ± 1.09 ^c	25.47 ± 2.33 ^c	41.41 ± 9.4 ^c	34.01 ± 1.75 ^c	7349.97 ± 208.62 ^a
1-Hexanol	14.698	16.41 ± 0.12 ^d	111.53 ± 11.42 ^c	40.95 ± 2.21 ^d	nd	17.58 ± 2.2 ^d		182.84 ± 1.63 ^b	294.46 ± 11.04 ^a
Cyclohexanol, 5-methyl-2-(1-methylethyl)-, (1 alpha,2 alpha,5 alpha)-	18.668	184.26 ± 10.57 ^a	296.01 ± 7.15 ^a	57.42 ± 5.35 ^a	94.93 ± 9.8 ^a	89.31 ± 9.83 ^a	0.68 ± NA ^a	186.77 ± 15.82 ^a	307.21 ± 297.88 ^a
Acids									
Acetic acid	16.261	13,650.27 ± 546.05 ^d	14,317.77 ± 2.8 ^d	1532.46 ± 357.84 ^e	127,706.27 _a ± 422.99	178.28 ± 84.41 ^e	64,781.75 ± 601.42 ^b	509.52 ± 437.28 ^e	24,235.09 ± 1862.02 _c
Hexanoic acid	20.987	166.24 ± 89.49 ^b	31.54 ± 4.88 ^b	49.2 ± 21.93 ^b	431.23 ± 54.13 ^a	1.78 ± 1.1 ^b	411.28 ± 95.31 ^a	2.23 ± 1.46 ^b	476.61 ± 33.31 ^a
Esters									
Ethyl acetate	4.686	nd	19,507.83 ± 13,862.91 ^{ab}	5714.25 ± 269.57 ^b	1339.17 ± 204.63 ^b	14,536.18 _b ± 1162.92	554.21 ± 16.95 ^b	39,721.29 ± 2156.6 ^a	1799.73 ± 423.73 ^b
Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	25.010	3.88 ± 1.82 ^b	4.47 ± 1.62 ^b	8.78 ± 0.26 ^b	208.63 ± 23.3 ^a	2.77 ± 1.23 ^b	3.08 ± 0.65 ^b	nd	4.54 ± 0.05 ^b
Amides									
Acetamide	20.331	47.2 ± 0.31 ^d	234.62 ± 17.47 ^b	6.44 ± 2.03 ^d	1079.85 ± 24.98 ^a	4.87 ± 0.88 ^d	136.38 ± 7.36 ^c	8.76 ± 5.35 ^d	195.83 ± 4.62 ^b
Unknowns									
Unknown 1, <i>m/z</i> 69	14.032	215.55 ± 39.5 ^{ab}	176.17 ± 21.3 ^{abc}	145.33 ± 11.07 ^{bcd}	199.26 ± 4.94 ^{abc}	166.22 ± 6.44 ^{bc}	243.06 ± 16.67 ^a	138.89 ± 0.57 ^{cd}	87.27 ± 9.47 ^d
Unknown 2, <i>m/z</i> 67	19.940	nd	8.37 ± 2.17 ^b	10.8 ± 0.46 ^b	14.11 ± 0.42 ^b	2.83 ± 0.49 ^b	1.98 ± 0.89 ^b	513.94 ± 28.94 ^a	1.96 ± 0.01 ^b
Unknown 3, <i>m/z</i> 82	20.053	1086.99 ± 137.42 ^a	8.4 ± 0.8 ^b	nd	883.09 ± 6.8 ^a	nd	17.8 ± 1.08 ^b	nd	nd
Sulphur compounds									
Dimethyl sulphide	3.122	803,874.15 ± 16,324.54 ^d	135,0777.42 ± 43,144.17 ^b	nd	6895.24 ± 357.64 ^e	nd	1,453,699.47 ± 2221.11 ^a	nd	1,233,579.89 ± 26,571.4 ^c
Disulphide, dimethyl	9.54	4416.16 ± 291.13 ^c	11,878.38 ± 111.17 ^b	nd	2074.91 ± 84.32 ^{de}	467.65 ± 114.18 ^e	29,989.09 ± 1042.18 _a	nd	3626.47 ± 388.05 ^{cd}

Table 4. Cont.

VOC	Retention Time (min)	PT (AAU·10 ³)	TC (AAU·10 ³)	CV (AAU·10 ³)	NO (AAU·10 ³)	SA (AAU·10 ³)	TL (AAU·10 ³)	AP (AAU·10 ³)	SC (AAU·10 ³)
2,4-Dithiapentane	13.874	nd	1282.94 ± 71.13 ^{ab}	nd	nd	nd	3087.88 ± 696.66 ^a	nd	1237.12 ± 288.68 ^b
Unknown S-compound Rt14.8	14.814	247.85 ± 0.67 ^d	2384.52 ± 354.73 ^b	nd	152.97 ± 26.56 ^d	nd	4191.94 ± 141.16 ^a	nd	1410.65 ± 211.03 ^c
Unknown S-compound Rt15.4	15.443	134.4 ± 0.03 ^b	353.85 ± 6.85 ^b	nd	445.18 ± 1.94 ^b	nd	3892.75 ± 104.06 ^a	nd	183.37 ± 141.07 ^b
Unknown S-compound Rt15.9	15.97	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	1681.78 ± 2.83	nd	nd
Unknown S-compound Rt16.4	16.409	285.7 ± 9.15 ^b	208.78 ± 0.23 ^b	nd	nd	nd	15,310.03 ± 1596.56 _a	nd	989.82 ± 132.16 ^b
Unknown S-compound Rt17.4	17.407	4609.8 ± 421.57 ^b	217.69 ± 1.6 ^d	nd	1923.43 ± 576.21 ^c	nd	36,422.04 ± 298.37 ^a	nd	nd
Unknown S-compound Rt17.8	17.842	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	16,275.36 ± 1029.97	nd	nd
Dimethylsulphoxide	18.406	227,822.08 ± 15,166.45 ^b	322,656.57 ± 4499.06 ^a	26,226.88 ± 7588.75 _d	82,760.22 ± 7421.34 _c	32,747.46 ± 3511.28 _d	294,858.28 ± 18,723.79 ^a	2790.73 ± 700.01 ^d	300,139.38 ± 4896.15 ^a
Dimethylsulphone	22.107	39,726.38 ± 1205.58 _a	22,154.38 ± 205.36 ^{bc}	1070.91 ± 575.09 ^e	4863.89 ± 465.73 ^d	1068.1 ± 306.73 ^e	20,389.32 ± 231.65 ^c	96.76 ± 0.54 ^e	24,175.13 ± 165.6 ^b
Benzothiazole	22.733	595.14 ± 55.71 ^c	781.28 ± 103.88 ^c	6206.46 ± 760.92 ^a	288.83 ± 1.66 ^c	6388.55 ± 0.99 ^a	686.69 ± 30.64 ^c	2213.77 ± 116.99 ^b	521.77 ± 62.29 ^c
Unknown S-compound Rt25.6	25.639	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	40,046.27 ± 19,503.25	nd	nd
Unknown S-compound Rt27.3	27.31	nd	nd	175.78 ± 31.52 ^b	nd	316.7 ± 3.25 ^a	nd	nd	nd

(PT) *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, (TC) *Tetraselmis chuii*, (CV) *Chlorella vulgaris*, (NO) *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, (SA) *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, (TL) *Tisochrysis lutea*, (AP) *Arthrospira platensis*, and (SC) *Skeletonema costatum*. Different superscript letters within the same row indicate statistically significant differences between strains (Tukey's HSD test, $p < 0.05$).

Alcohols, which can impart alcoholic, ethereal, medicinal, fermented, and occasionally fruity or green notes, were detected in varying amounts, with the highest level of 35% in *SC* and the lowest (<1%) in *AP*. Although alcohol is often perceived as pleasant when moderate in concentration, its strong character can occasionally be overwhelming [38,43]. Acids exhibited the most extensive variation among the microalgae, ranging from <1% to 90% (*SA* vs. *TL*). Their characteristic sharp, sour and cheesy notes can be agreeable at low levels but become unappealing at higher concentrations. The presence of acids in dried microalgal powders can also influence the pH of aqueous solutions. Esters, known for their pleasant sweet, fruity and sometimes ethereal and creamy aromas reminiscent of grape, cherry, milk or vanilla, were generally present at low abundances (<5%) in *TL*, *NO*, *PT*, and *SC*. By contrast, significantly higher levels (44–55%) were found in *SA*, *CV*, and *AP*, contributing to their aromatic profile. The amide group was represented solely by acetamide with a generally low abundance (<1%); the molecule has no specifically known aroma. Sulphur compounds, despite their low abundance in *NO*, *SA*, *CV*, and *AP* (<1%), were notably more prevalent in other samples (17–30%). As the human olfactory system is highly sensitive to sulphur compounds (odour thresholds in water of 6.65–80 ppb; see Supplementary Table S1), even small amounts can have a significant impact on the perceived aroma. Sulphur compounds can evoke aromas similar to those in cabbage, onion/garlic, fish, and rotten eggs [38]. The influence of the VOCs we categorised as unknown compounds is not discussed, as their structures and substance classes are unclear.

The high abundance of esters and the low abundance of sulphur compounds (especially dimethyl sulphide, which is associated with a fishy taste) in *CV* and *AP* could explain why they have a long history of use as food [44]. Moreover, *SA* is identified as providing a pleasant aroma with a low amount of sulphur compounds comparable to the aroma of *CV*. *TC* has been found to possess a balanced, complex aroma with many pleasant compound groups; however, it also has a high level of sulphur compounds and acids, which could affect the pleasant aroma.

4. Conclusions

Interest in microalgae as a sustainable food source is rapidly increasing; however, to date, industrial-scale exploitation has been predominantly limited to two species: *A. platensis* and *C. vulgaris*. This study investigated six alternative microalgal strains (*Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Tetraselmis chunii*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, *Tisochrysis lutea*, and *Skeletonema costatum*) demonstrating their significant potential for industrial-scale applications in the food sector by offering a nutritional density comparable to these established commercial standards.

Proteins were the most abundant macromolecule for most of these organisms, with concentration values ranging from 31.2 to 65.9% and high levels of essential amino acids, notably arginine and tryptophan. In addition to their protein profile, several microalgae showed carbohydrate contents of approximately 30%. Furthermore, the strains *NO*, *TL*, and *TC* exhibited the highest lipid content, highlighting their potential for diversified applications in the food sector.

Different volatile organic compounds were observed among the strains studied, playing an important role in determining the aromatic potential for industrial applications. Strains belonging to the genera *Chlorella*, *Arthrospira*, and *Scenedesmus* presented high ester and low sulphur compound levels, contributing to a pleasant, fruity aromatic profile favourable for sensory acceptance. In contrast, the complex aroma with high acid and sulphur contents of other strains could negatively impact palatability, requiring specific technological processing, such as deodorization, to improve their organoleptic properties.

Finally, while strains like *T. chuii* are already authorised in the EU, the industrial exploitation of the other promising strains must still address regulatory and safety considerations.

The detailed physicochemical profiling provided here establishes a robust analytical baseline of alternative microalgal strains, positioning these less-exploited microalgae as high-value alternatives and paving the way for their formal recognition as novel foods in the global market.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/foods15050809/s1>. Table S1: Aroma and analysis properties of the different compounds identified in this study.

Author Contributions: C.M.-M.: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing—original draft; S.V.-C.: Investigation; L.K.T.: Investigation, Writing—original draft; D.K.: Investigation; F.J.A.: Investigation; M.G.-V.: Investigation; T.L.: Formal analysis, Writing—original draft; Funding acquisition. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, the European Union, and the Government of Andalusia, grant numbers PID2024-156976OB-C22, PID2022-136292OB-I00, PLSQ_2023_00233, and PCM_00083, respectively.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Materials. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: This work is part of the SOLAR-FOODS (PID2022-136292OB-I00) and PHOTO-BIO+ (PID2024-156976OB-C22) projects, funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033) and the European Union (FEDER). This work was also supported by the RE·USE project (PLSQ_2023_00233), funded by the Government of Andalusia and the European Regional Development Fund, and BLUE-FUTURE (PCM_00083), funded by the Government of Andalusia and the European Union. The authors would like to thank PPIT-UAL, Junta de Andalusia-FEDER 2021-2027 (CPRE2023-076), and the Juan de la Cierva (JDC2022-048280-I) and Ramon y Cajal (RYC2021-031061-I) programmes, both funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AP	Arthrospira platensis
CV	Chlorella vulgaris
DHA	docosahexaenoic acid
EPA	eicosapentaenoic acid
EU	European Union
FAME	fatty acid methyl ester
ME	methyl ester
ND	not detected
NO	Nannochloropsis oceanica
PT	Phaeodactylum tricornutum
PUFA	polyunsaturated fatty acids
SA	Scenedesmus almeriensis
SC	Skeletonema costatum
TC	Tetraselmis chuii
TL	Tisochrysis lutea
VOC	volatile organic compound

References

1. Čmiková, N.; Vukić, M.D.; Vukovic, N.L.; Havlík, J.; Noguera-Artiaga, L.; Carbonell-Barrachina, Á.A.; Jančo, I.; Vinciguerra, V.; Garzoli, S.; Kačániová, M. Comprehensive Analysis of *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Arthrospira platensis*: Algae for Food Well-Being and Sustainable Agriculture. *ACS Food Sci. Technol.* **2025**, *5*, 3000–3011. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
2. Kelebek, H.; Uzlasir, T.; Sasmaz, H.K. Bioactive Compounds and Health Benefits of *Arthrospira platensis* and *Chlorella vulgaris*: A Comprehensive Review. *Food Nutr.* **2025**, *1*, 100033. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
3. Giroto, F.; Scapini, A. Microalgal Biomass in the European Food Industry: Navigating Regulation, Technological Innovation, and Consumer Acceptance. *Algal Res.* **2025**, *91*, 104288. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
4. Çelekli, A.; Özbal, B.; Bozkurt, H. Challenges in Functional Food Products with the Incorporation of Some Microalgae. *Foods* **2024**, *13*, 725. [\[CrossRef\]](#) [\[PubMed\]](#)
5. Chen, C.; Tang, T.; Shi, Q.; Zhou, Z.; Fan, J. The Potential and Challenge of Microalgae as Promising Future Food Sources. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* **2022**, *126*, 99–112. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
6. Rivera-Sánchez, E.; Villaró-Cos, S.; Salinas-García, M.; Lafarga, T. Increasing the Sustainability of Photoautotrophic Microalgae Production by Minimising Freshwater Requirements. *New Biotechnol.* **2025**, *86*, 14–24. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
7. Villaró-Cos, S.; Guzmán Sánchez, J.L.; Acién, G.; Lafarga, T. Research Trends and Current Requirements and Challenges in the Industrial Production of *Spirulina* as a Food Source. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* **2024**, *143*, 104280. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
8. Colusse, G.A.; Mendes, C.R.B.; Duarte, M.E.R.; Carvalho, J.C.d.; Nosedá, M.D. Effects of Different Culture Media on Physiological Features and Laboratory Scale Production Cost of *Dunaliella salina*. *Biotechnol. Rep.* **2020**, *27*, e00508. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
9. Debnath, T.; Bandyopadhyay, T.K.; Vanitha, K.; Bobby, M.N.; Nath Tiwari, O.; Bhunia, B.; Muthuraj, M. Astaxanthin from Microalgae: A Review on Structure, Biosynthesis, Production Strategies and Application. *Food Res. Int.* **2024**, *176*, 113841. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
10. Pereira, H.; Sá, M.; Maia, I.; Rodrigues, A.; Teles, I.; Wijffels, R.H.; Navalho, J.; Barbosa, M. Fucoxanthin Production from *Tisochrysis lutea* and *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* at Industrial Scale. *Algal Res.* **2021**, *56*, 102322. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
11. Celi, C.; Fino, D.; Savorani, F. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* as a Source of Value-Added Products: A Review on Recent Developments in Cultivation and Extraction Technologies. *Bioresour. Technol. Rep.* **2022**, *19*, 101122. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
12. Gao, F.; Cabanelas, I.T.D.; Wijffels, R.H.; Barbosa, M.J. Fucoxanthin and Docosahexaenoic Acid Production by Cold-Adapted *Tisochrysis lutea*. *New Biotechnol.* **2022**, *66*, 16–24. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
13. Villaró, S.; Acién, G.; Alarcón, J.; Ruiz, Á.; Rodríguez-Chikri, L.; Viviano, E.; Lafarga, T. A Zero-Waste Approach for the Production and Use of *Arthrospira platensis* as a Protein Source in Foods and as a Plant Biostimulant in Agriculture. *J. Appl. Phycol.* **2023**, *35*, 2619–2630. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
14. Jesionowska, M.; Ovadia, J.; Hockemeyer, K.; Clews, A.C.; Xu, Y. EPA and DHA in Microalgae: Health Benefits, Biosynthesis, and Metabolic Engineering Advances. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *100*, 831–842. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
15. Patel, A.K.; Albarico, F.P.J.B.; Perumal, P.K.; Vadrale, A.P.; Ntan, C.T.; Chau, H.T.B.; Anwar, C.; Wani, H.M.u.d.; Pal, A.; Saini, R.; et al. Algae as an Emerging Source of Bioactive Pigments. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *351*, 126910. [\[CrossRef\]](#) [\[PubMed\]](#)
16. Moran, L.; Bou, G.; Aldai, N.; Ciardi, M.; Morillas-España, A.; Sánchez-Zurano, A.; Barron, L.J.R.; Lafarga, T. Characterisation of the Volatile Profile of Microalgae and Cyanobacteria Using Solid-Phase Microextraction Followed by Gas Chromatography Coupled to Mass Spectrometry. *Sci. Rep.* **2022**, *12*, 3661. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
17. Salinas-García, M.; Calatrava-Arrizabalaga, P.; Ciardi, M.; Villaró-Cos, S.; Lafarga, T. Development and Reutilisation of a Fertiliser-Based Culture Medium for the Commercial Production of *Chlorella sorokiniana*. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 23891. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
18. Aguirre, J. The Kjeldahl Method. In *The Kjeldahl Method: 140 Years*; Aguirre, J., Ed.; Springer Nature: Cham, Switzerland, 2023; pp. 53–78, ISBN 978-3-031-31458-2.
19. Folch, J.; Lees, M.; SloaneStanley, G.H. A Simple Method for the Isolation and Purification of Total Lipides from Animal Tissues. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1957**, *226*, 497–509. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
20. UNE-EN 17605:2022; Algae and Algae Products—Methods of Sampling and Analysis—Sample Treatment. AENOR: Madrid, Spain, 2022.
21. Bongiorno, T.; Foglio, L.; Proietti, L.; Vasconi, M.; Lopez, A.; Pizzera, A.; Carminati, D.; Tava, A.; Vizcaíno, A.J.; Alarcón, F.J.; et al. Microalgae from Biorefinery as Potential Protein Source for Siberian Sturgeon (*A. baerii*) Aquafeed. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 8779. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
22. Garcia-Vaquero, M.; Rajauria, G.; Miranda, M.; Sweeney, T.; Lopez-Alonso, M.; O'Doherty, J. Seasonal Variation of the Proximate Composition, Mineral Content, Fatty Acid Profiles and Other Phytochemical Constituents of Selected Brown Macroalgae. *Mar. Drugs* **2021**, *19*, 204. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
23. Fuchsmann, P.; Tena Stern, M.; Bischoff, P.; Badertscher, R.; Breme, K.; Walther, B. Development and Performance Evaluation of a Novel Dynamic Headspace Vacuum Transfer “In Trap” Extraction Method for Volatile Compounds and Comparison with Headspace Solid-Phase Microextraction and Headspace in-Tube Extraction. *J. Chromatogr. A* **2019**, *1601*, 60–70. [\[CrossRef\]](#)

24. Sumner, L.W.; Amberg, A.; Barrett, D.; Beale, M.H.; Beger, R.; Daykin, C.A.; Fan, T.W.M.; Fiehn, O.; Goodacre, R.; Griffin, J.L.; et al. Proposed Minimum Reporting Standards for Chemical Analysis: Chemical Analysis Working Group (CAWG) Metabolomics Standards Initiative (MSI). *Metabolomics* **2007**, *3*, 211–221. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
25. Finkel, Z.V.; Follows, M.J.; Liefer, J.D.; Brown, C.M.; Benner, I.; Irwin, A.J. Phylogenetic Diversity in the Macromolecular Composition of Microalgae. *PLoS ONE* **2016**, *11*, e0155977. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
26. Cui, Y.; Thomas-Hall, S.R.; Schenk, P.M. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* Microalgae as a Rich Source of Omega-3 Oil: Progress in Lipid Induction Techniques towards Industry Adoption. *Food Chem.* **2019**, *297*, 124937. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
27. Figueiredo, A.R.P.; da Costa, E.; Silva, J.; Domingues, M.R.; Domingues, P. The Effects of Different Extraction Methods of Lipids from *Nannochloropsis oceanica* on the Contents of Omega-3 Fatty Acids. *Algal Res.* **2019**, *41*, 101556. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Lafarga, T. Effect of Microalgal Biomass Incorporation into Foods: Nutritional and Sensorial Attributes of the End Products. *Algal Res.* **2019**, *41*, 101566. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. de Carvalho Silvello, M.A.; Severo Gonçalves, I.; Patrícia Held Azambuja, S.; Silva Costa, S.; Garcia Pereira Silva, P.; Oliveira Santos, L.; Goldbeck, R. Microalgae-Based Carbohydrates: A Green Innovative Source of Bioenergy. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2022**, *344*, 126304. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Ahamefule, C.S.; Ogbonna, C.N.; Ahamefule, B.C.; Ogbonna, I.; Ogbonna, J. Lipids and Fatty Acids from Microalgae. In *Handbook of Food and Feed from Microalgae: Production, Application, Regulation, and Sustainability*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2023; Volume 174, pp. 73–86. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Garrido-Cardenas, J.A.; Manzano-Agugliari, F.; Acien-Fernandez, F.G.; Molina-Grima, E. Microalgae Research Worldwide. *Algal Res.* **2018**, *35*, 50–60. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Bellou, S.; Baeshen, M.N.; Elazzazy, A.M.; Aggeli, D.; Sayegh, F.; Aggelis, G. Microalgal Lipids Biochemistry and Biotechnological Perspectives. *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2014**, *32*, 1476–1493. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Lafarga, T. Cultured Microalgae and Compounds Derived Thereof for Food Applications: Strain Selection and Cultivation, Drying, and Processing Strategies. *Food Rev. Int.* **2020**, *36*, 559–583. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Markou, G.; Chentir, I.; Eliopoulos, C.; Arapoglou, D.; Vaquero, M.G.; Tiwari, B. Microalgae as a Source of Alternative Protein. In *Handbook of Food and Feed from Microalgae: Production, Application, Regulation, and Sustainability*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2023; Volume 27, pp. 59–71. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Andreeva, A.; Budenkova, E.; Babich, O.; Sukhikh, S.; Ulrikh, E.; Ivanova, S.; Prosekov, A.; Dolganyuk, V. Production, Purification, and Study of the Amino Acid Composition of Microalgae Proteins. *Molecules* **2021**, *26*, 2767. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
36. Sá, M.; Ferrer-Ledo, N.; Wijffels, R.; Crespo, J.G.; Barbosa, M.; Galinha, C.F. Monitoring of Eicosapentaenoic Acid (EPA) Production in the Microalgae *Nannochloropsis oceanica*. *Algal Res.* **2020**, *45*, 101766. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Stasiewicz, A.; Conde, T.; Gęgotek, A.; Domingues, M.R.; Domingues, P.; Skrzydlewska, E. Prevention of UVB Induced Metabolic Changes in Epidermal Cells by Lipid Extract from Microalgae *Nannochloropsis oceanica*. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2023**, *24*, 11302. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
38. Isleten Hosoglu, M. Aroma Characterization of Five Microalgae Species Using Solid-Phase Microextraction and Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry/Olfactometry. *Food Chem.* **2018**, *240*, 1210–1218. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Nass, P.P.; Zepka, L.Q. Volatile Organic Compounds as Food/Feed Ingredients. In *Handbook of Food and Feed from Microalgae: Production, Application, Regulation, and Sustainability*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2023; Volume 31, pp. 181–187. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Colonia, B.S.O.; de Melo Pereira, G.V.; Carvalho, J.C.d.; Karp, S.G.; Rodrigues, C.; Soccol, V.T.; Fanka, L.S.; Soccol, C.R. Deodorization of Algae Biomass to Overcome Off-Flavors and Odor Issues for Developing New Food Products: Innovations, Trends, and Applications. *Food Chem. Adv.* **2023**, *2*, 100270. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Zhou, L.; Chen, J.; Xu, J.; Li, Y.; Zhou, C.; Yan, X. Change of Volatile Components in Six Microalgae with Different Growth Phases. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* **2017**, *97*, 761–769. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Van Durme, J.; Goiris, K.; De Winne, A.; De Cooman, L.; Muylaert, K. Evaluation of the Volatile Composition and Sensory Properties of Five Species of Microalgae. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2013**, *61*, 10881–10890. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Murray, A.M.; Fotidis, I.A.; Isenschmid, A.; Haxthausen, K.R.A.; Angelidaki, I. Wirelessly Powered Submerged-Light Illuminated Photobioreactors for Efficient Microalgae Cultivation. *Algal Res.* **2017**, *25*, 244–251. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Coleman, B.; Van Poucke, C.; Dewitte, B.; Ruttens, A.; Moerdijk-Poortvliet, T.; Latsos, C.; De Reu, K.; Blommaert, L.; Duquenne, B.; Timmermans, K.; et al. Potential of Microalgae as Flavoring Agents for Plant-Based Seafood Alternatives. *Future Foods* **2022**, *5*, 100139. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.